

**CRIMINOLOGY GRADUATES OF NOTRE DAME OF SALAMAN
COLLEGE, INCORPORATED FROM 2010-2020:
A TRACER STUDY**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 2

Pages: 316-338

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2351

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13766076

Manuscript Accepted: 07-27-2024

Criminology Graduates of Notre Dame of Salaman College, Incorporated From 2010-2020: A Tracer Study

Cha – Cha A. Guiral, * Marnie J. Besas

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to collect data on the status of Bachelor of Science in Criminology graduates over the past ten years through a descriptive study by using a validated survey questionnaire. The respondents of this were the 252 graduates. Total enumeration was utilized in getting the desired sample of the population. The research was conducted at Lebak, Sultan Kudarat precisely at Notre Dame of Salaman College, Inc. Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were formulated: Majority of the graduates were male and in terms of age, civil status, majority were married and were 23 y.o. and below. In connection with the highest educational attainment, majority were criminology graduates. For their present employment status and initial monthly income gross, majority were regular and earned P25, 000 and above. Majority had human relation skills. The most graduates who passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination was in 2019 out of all the years from 2010 to 2020. According to their current job status, the largest percentage of employed graduates was from 2019. Only 5 of those who proceeded to advanced studies. From 2010 to 2020, the number of graduates working in their field of choice were employed as criminologists; the highest number of these graduates working in their field were those who graduated in 2019.

Keywords: *criminal justice, tracer study, criminology graduates, quantitative research, descriptive survey, philippines*

Introduction

Tracing the Criminology graduates from year 2010-2020 was been the goal of the researcher as well as to determine their status after graduating from Notre Dame of Salaman College, Inc. There were different concerns needed to in order to meet relevant data in the fulfilment of the study. A thorough survey was challenging but had a significant role in enhancing the teaching strategies, applicable development plan that can strengthen the curriculum (Albina & Sumagaysay, 2020; Asuncion, 2019).

Furthermore, it can also be used for continuous improvement, in which it helps identify areas where the school can improve its curriculum, teachings methods, and support systems based on the outcomes of its graduates. Following the success of alumni fosters a strong sense of community, encourages networking, and can lead to beneficial partnerships or contributions. Moreover, monitoring a graduate's career paths aids in aligning the curriculum with industry demands, improving job placement rates, and preparing students for successful careers. Finally, positive outcomes of graduates enhance the school's reputation and can attract potential students and stakeholders (Aydinan, 2019; Dela Cruz, 2022).

Notre Dame of Salaman College, Inc. (NDSC) as an institution upholds its mission to produce competent graduates of Bachelor of Science in Criminology. This is a four- year program which aims to impose discipline, academic excellence, valuable training. It is a program, which emphasizes leadership and service toward the doctrine of being a law-abiding person, which culminates with the Criminologist Licensure Examination (CLE). In the past years, NDSC continuously hones and sharpens young minds to become peacemakers and agents of goodwill. Criminology graduates are performing their job frequently in various places with different people and circumstances. Their work signifies their utmost desire and their commitment to be in a long, tiring, but meaningful duty for the country (Pentang et al., 2022; Salmo et al., 2022).

Having the reputable record of graduates, the Department of Criminology failed to trace their alumni to the point of having little to no updates and information about their state or condition after graduation. Hence, the researcher was determined to trace the existing situation of its alumni from 2010-2020. Tracing the growth and development of graduates and products of the institution is crucial for several reasons. In terms of quality assessment, tracking their achievements and progress provides insights into the effectiveness of the school's education and programs (Cooper et al., 2019; Cuadra et al., 2019).

Hence, the researcher conducted this study to delineate the profile of graduates, offering valuable insights into the caliber of education provided and evaluating the efficacy of the program. Additionally, it equips the institution with the necessary foresight to adapt and enhance its offerings in response to real-world outcomes experienced by its alumni. The findings of this study would contribute to the body of research aimed at enhancing and refining the curriculum, paving the way for the formulation of a comprehensive development plan for the Criminology Program within the institution.

Research Questions

This study aimed to trace the Criminology Graduates of Notre Dame of Salaman College, Incorporated from 2010 to 2020. More specifically, this study focused to achieve on the following objectives:

1. To determine the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. age;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5. professional examination passed;
 - 1.6. present employment status;
 - 1.7. present job level position;
 - 1.8. initial gross monthly earning; and
 - 1.9. competencies learned in college which is useful to job.
2. To ascertain the number of graduates who passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination from 2010 to 2020.
3. To know the present employment status of the Criminology graduates from 2010 to 2020.
4. To determine the number of graduates who proceeded to advanced studies.
5. To find out how many of the graduates employed in line with their chosen profession as criminology graduates from 2010 to 2020.
6. To determine the reasons causing a mismatch between graduates' current employment and their chosen profession from 2010 to 2020.
7. To create an intervention program based on the results of the study.

Methodology

This section presents the research design to be used, the place where it was conducted, the population and its sampling, the survey questionnaire and its data collection, the statistical treatment of the gathered data, and the ethical considerations.

Research Design

The researcher employed quantitative research utilizing a descriptive survey design in collecting and gathering information on the status of the graduates of Bachelor of Science in Criminology for the past 10 years using a validated survey questionnaire. Descriptive Survey Design is a quantitative method that focuses on describing the characteristics of a phenomenon rather than asking why it occurs. Doing so helps us better understand its nature and gives a good foundation for further research (Cooksey & Cooksey, 2020).

The goal of quantitative research design is to collect numerical data and generalize it to different populations. In this design, all aspects are meticulously and precisely planned before data collection, and the researcher has a clearly defined research question to which objective answers are sought. Statistics and numbers are examples of data. The project can be used to investigate causal relationships, predict future outcomes, or more broadly generalize concepts (Cooksey & Cooksey, 2020).

A quantitative research design is referred to as a quantitative research design. The method used, such as telephone interviews, in-person interviews, online surveys, or surveys sent by mail, affected the design. Other methodologies included physical counts or SMS/Test Message surveys. The goal of quantitative research design is to ascertain the proportion of people who hold a given belief, behavior, or emotion. Large sample sizes are common in quantitative projects, which focus on the volume of responses rather than the more nuanced or emotional understanding that qualitative research seeks to elicit. Each respondent is typically asked the same questions in a quantitative research design, which ensures that the entire data sample can be fairly analyzed. The data is provided in a numerical format and can be analyzed statistically in a quantifiable way. However, surveys can be designed to diverge if a respondent answers in a particular way. For instance, people who are satisfied or dissatisfied with a service may ask different questions later (Rahman, 2020).

In quantitative research, closed-ended questions are often favored due to their efficiency. Without a predetermined list of options, respondents typically struggle to provide detailed open-ended responses. This approach ensures the effectiveness of the quantitative research process, sparing researchers the labor-intensive task of coding numerous open-ended responses. However, quantitative research designs often allow for the inclusion of an "Other" category among the answer choices, enabling respondents who do not neatly fit into existing categories to provide accurate responses. This practice ensures that all responses are captured and can be utilized in analyzing research findings (Swart et al., 2019).

Moreover, quantitative research designs most often reflect a deterministic philosophy that is rooted in the post-positivist paradigm, or school of thought. Post-positivists examine cause and how different causes can interact and/or influence outcomes. The post-positivist paradigm adopts the philosophy that reality can be discovered, however only imperfectly and in a probabilistic sense. The approach is typically deductive - where most ideas or concepts are reduced into variables and the relationship between or among them is tested. The knowledge that results is based on careful observation, measurement, and interpretation of objective reality (Sürücü & Maslacki, 2020).

By conducting descriptive survey research, we focus on the nature of a phenomenon without asking what its causes are. The main goal is to shed light on the heart of the research problem and better understand it. This method consists of creating questionnaires and distributing them to respondents, who then answer the questions. The descriptive survey method enables gathering vast data from a

heterogeneous audience. The survey design helps to analyze the frequencies and identify patterns in the survey responses (Cooksey & Cooksey, 2020).

Along with this, emphasized that descriptive research is a purposive process of gathering, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about the prevailing conditions, practices, beliefs, processes, trends, and cause-and-effect relationships, thereby making adequate and accurate interpretations about such data with or without the aid of a statistical method. Descriptive research reveals an in-depth understanding of a phenomenon. To precisely define the population, market, or circumstance, researchers from a variety of fields use descriptive research. To give you accurate and pertinent information, descriptive survey research uses a combination of quantitative and qualitative data. Descriptive survey design, a quick research technique, engages the subjects who are the focus of the study's goal (Millner et al., 2020).

Participants

The respondents for this comprehensive research endeavor encompassed the entirety of Criminology graduates from Notre Dame of Salaman College, Incorporated spanning the academic years of 2010 to 2020. There are 252 total number of graduates with the number of graduates yearly as: 8 in 2010, 26 in 2011, 20 in 2012, 15 in 2013, 9 in 2014, 12 in 2015, 12 in 2016, 24 in 2017, 39 in 2018, 64 in 2019, and 23 in 2020.

This extensive scope ensured that the study encapsulated a robust cross-section of individuals who have completed their education in the field of Criminology within the stipulated timeframe. By enlisting the entirety of Criminology graduates as respondents, the study aimed to engender a heightened sense of validity and legitimacy, as it endeavored to comprehensively represent the experiences and trajectories of this particular cohort of graduates.

The researcher established specific inclusion criteria for selecting the respondents, irrespective of gender, religion, or ethnicity. The focus was on Criminology graduates from Notre Dame of Salaman College, Incorporated, spanning from the academic years 2010 to 2020. Conversely, graduates who did not meet the criteria were excluded from participation, as were those unwilling or unable to provide consent or cooperate during the data collection.

The respondents had the right to withdraw from the study at any point, with assurances that their decision would not adversely affect their relationship with the school or program. Additionally, measures were in place to address any discomfort, distress, or emotional unease experienced by the respondents during the study, ensuring their well-being remained a priority throughout the research process. They were assured that they could opt out of the study at any juncture without fear of negative repercussions on their standing with the school or program.

Instruments

The tracer study questionnaire developed by CHED was used. This questionnaire had two parts; Part I – on Biographical Data covered personal data, educational background, employment characteristics, employment history, professional achievement, and transition, while Part II - is on Retrospective Evaluation of the Program covered satisfaction with the services, learning environment, facilities, adequacy of skills learned, adequacy and relevance of curricular program in terms of competencies. This tracer study questionnaire was used to obtain quantitative feedback from the graduates about their course-related skills, attitudes, reactions, and suggestions. Part of this tracer study questionnaire was a rating scale intended to determine the adequacy and relevance of the course competencies of the program. The questionnaire was given to a group of experts to check and review carefully.

The researcher then assessed the first version of the questionnaire to make sure the questions were clear, relevant, and complete. After that, she distributed a questionnaire to a small group of people who were similar to the target audience. This was to find out if there were any problems and to make sure the questions were good for the people who would answer them. Lastly, after a thorough scrutiny, the researcher did the final version of the questionnaire with well-structured questions. For this study, the questionnaire was made available to the graduate respondents through the web.

Data Collection

The researcher gathered data based on Igwenagu's (2016) book, "Fundamentals of Research Methodology and Data Collection," following several steps. First, she determined what data to collect. Second, she established the duration for data collection. Third, she selected a data collection strategy. Fourth, she collected, followed, analyzed, and applied the conclusions drawn from the data. Before proceeding, she obtained permission from the Notre Dame of Salaman College, which was reviewed and approved by the adviser. Copies were then provided to the school administrators where the study took place (Igwenagu, 2016).

The researcher adopted a research questionnaire which was attested by expert validators. Second, she sought approval from the Ethics and Review Committee and the Graduate School. Upon approval, permission was obtained from the Office of the Notre Dame of Salaman College, Incorporated. Fourth, the researcher reproduced the questionnaire as per the number of target respondents. After reproduction, she explained the Informed Consent Form (ICF) and administered the questionnaire, allowing ample time for completion. Sixth, upon retrieving questionnaires, she ensured all items were completed by participants. Finally, the completed questionnaires were summarized, tallied, analyzed, and interpreted.

Ethical Considerations

There is a major ethical consideration that has distinct implications for this quantitative research. These issues and concerns might come out basically from the methodology that was involved in this study. The ethical challenges that are applicable in this research concern were the issues of the proper operation of the study, confidentiality, and anonymity. This study followed the standards of the RMMC Ethics and Review Committee for the guidelines of ethical consideration, particularly in addressing the population and data such as, but not limited to:

Voluntary Participation. The respondents were granted the option to participate without any plan of repercussion reparations or loss of benefits. Therefore, after the purpose and the benefits of the study were shown to the participating person, the rights of the participant to provide the body of knowledge were carefully measured and foresighted upon. In this study, the respondents were not forced to be part of the study. They were free to withdraw their participation when they feel uncomfortable during the conduct of the study.

Privacy and confidentiality. Respondents have the right to privacy that should not be violated without informed consent to conform to the existing Data Privacy Act 2012, an act protecting the fundamental human right of privacy. One way of observing privacy and confidentiality in this quantitative research was to give options to the respondents for not indicating their names on the survey questionnaire. Besides, confidentiality and privacy were attained by not publishing the demographic data of the informants such as age, gender, occupation, employment, and disease if there was any. Hence, their identity was kept confidential for safety purposes. Even their responses to the items in the survey questionnaire were held and considered confidential.

Informed consent process. The prospective research respondents were fully informed about the objectives, methods, and benefits of the research as comprehensively as possible within the framework of the study. The consent of the respondents was obtained indicating that their participation was asked voluntarily. This was done in written form stating all the important details to be disclosed to the participants and the manner that which the survey was conducted. Since the respondents were consenting adults, there was no need to ask for parents' consent. The names of the respondents did not appear in the survey questionnaire and their answers were held confidential the respondents were fully aware that they can withdraw at any time from participating in the study.

Furthermore, any data that the researcher gathered was protected and the release of any information would follow through a strict informed consent process. The respondents would have a sense of control over their personal information to lessen their fear that the data or information would be used in any other unintended manner.

Recruitment. The respondents were informed of the reasons why they had become part of the study. For the respondents to understand what the study was all about; the researcher explained the purpose of the study so that they could further infer to the researcher and they could also view the essence of the study. Apart from the letter, the researcher gave the rationale of the study and its significance.

Risks. Research shall be conducted only if there is an acceptable positive benefit-risk ratio. In this study, the need to protect the respondents from significant harm was equally important. The study prioritized the welfare of the respondents. Furthermore, the respondents were not put in harm since their identity was held confidential. Their security and safety were of the utmost concern. As the researcher, there was a need to ensure that the respondents were physically, emotionally, and socially ready. In answering the survey questionnaire, the researcher made a way that the respondents did not feel discomfort or awkward.

Benefits. This study would be beneficial to the respondents since the results would serve as learnings for the institution and the administration to be more resourceful in terms of operating the Criminology program. The teachers could have more emphasis on teaching strategies to meet higher results for the board examination.

The persons involved had a wider and broader knowledge in regards to their leadership with the cooperation and active participation of the Criminology teachers as they went along working and promoting quality education. This study was conducted for a purpose: to serve its internal and external stakeholders, most especially the students.

Additionally, to achieve beneficence in research, the researcher the aspects that would not harm the lives of the respondents, and thus, would benefit from further undertakings with regard to the related studies.

Plagiarism. The study had no trace or evidence of misinterpretation of someone else's work. The study was subjected to plagiarism detectors like Grammarly software. As a researcher, there was need to have positive character and integrity, which are associated with moral virtues and values. The researcher must have better knowledge about the paradigm of plagiarism to have a credible research paper.

Fabrication. The study had no indication or cue of purposive misinterpretation of what had been done. There was no making up of data and results or purposefully putting forward conclusions that were not accurate. The researcher employed and integrated theories that were related to the information and other inferential concepts.

Falsification. The study had no trace of purposefully misrepresenting the work to fit a model or theoretical expectation and had no evidence of over-claiming or exaggeration. Added to that, this study did not adhere to manipulating the data, which involved formulating statements or disregarding important details, maneuvering materials, tools, or methodologies that would mislead others.

Conflict of Interest (COI). The study had no trace of conflict of interest, for example, the disclosure of COI, which is a set of conditions in which professional judgment concerning primary interest such as respondent's well-being or the validity of the research tends to be influenced by a secondary interest such as financial or academic gains or recognitions. Furthermore, the researcher had no control or influence over the respondents, forcing them to be part of the study.

Deceit. The study had no trace of misleading the respondents about any possible danger. There must be humongous protection of the rights of the respondents in any study, especially, that they have attained higher education, so balanced and appropriate principles shall be adhered to.

Authorship. The researcher of the study is currently enrolled in the RMMC Graduate School. The researcher had undergone a series of revisions for her thesis based on the suggestions and recommendations made by her adviser who guided the researcher throughout the completion of this paper. The refinement of the paper had been made possible through the guidance of her adviser. The researcher also followed the standards of the RMMC Ethics Review Committee for the guidelines of ethical consideration.

Results

This section presents the data on the profile of the graduates in terms of sex, age, civil status, highest educational attainment, professional examination have passed, present employment status, present job level position, initial gross monthly earnings, and competencies learned in college, which are useful to their job.

3.1. The Profile of the Respondents in terms of Sex

Table 1 presents the data on the profile of the respondents in terms of sex. Frequency count and percentage were used to treat the gathered data.

The table illustrates the gender distribution among graduates across different years. In 2010, 6 or 75% were male, and 2 or 25% were female. In 2011, there were 12 male graduates, accounted for 46%, and 14 females, comprising 54%. Similarly, in 2012, there were 18 males, which was 90%, and 2 females, made up 10%. In 2013, 13 males graduated, represented 87%, while 2 females accounted for 13%. In 2014, there was 1 male graduate, or 11%, and 8 females, or 89%. Moving to 2015, there were 7 male graduates to comprise 58%, and 5 females to constitute 42%. In 2016, 6 graduates were male, represented 50%, and 6 were female, accounted for 50%. In 2017, 16 males graduated, comprised 67%, and 8 females, made up 33%. In 2018, 27 males graduated, represented 69%, while 12 females accounted for 31%. In 2019, there were 58 male graduates, to make up 91%, and 6 females, comprised 9%. Finally, in 2020, the 20 male graduates, represented 87%, and 3 females, accounted for 13%.

Analyzing the results, it was evident that 2019 had the highest number of graduates, totaling 64, with 58 males and 6 females.

Table 1. The Profile of the Respondents in terms of Sex

<i>Year Graduated</i>		<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
2010	Male	6	75
	Female	2	25
	Total	8	100
2011	Male	12	46
	Female	14	54
	Total	26	100
2012	Male	18	90
	Female	2	10
	Total	20	100
2013	Male	13	87
	Female	2	13
	Total	15	100
2014	Male	1	11
	Female	8	89
	Total	9	100
2015	Male	7	58
	Female	5	42
	Total	12	100
2016	Male	6	50
	Female	6	50
	Total	12	100
2017	Male	16	67
	Female	8	33
	Total	24	100
2018	Male	27	69
	Female	12	39
	Total	39	100

2019	Male	58	91
	Female	6	9
	Total	64	100
2020	Male	20	87
	Female	3	13
	Total	23	100
Total		252	

3.2. The Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Table 2 presents the data on the profile of the graduates in terms of age. Frequency count and percentage were used to treat the gathered data. The table provides a detailed breakdown of the age distribution among graduates in various years. In 2010, out of the total 8 graduates, 5 or 63% were aged 23 and below, indicating a predominance of younger graduates. Additionally, 2 graduates, or 25%, fell within the age range of 24 to 26 years old, while 1 graduate, or 12%, was between 27 and 28 years old. This suggested a relatively diverse age range among the graduating cohort.

Moving to 2011, a similar trend emerged, with 20 graduates, or 77%, being 23 years old and below, indicating a significant proportion of younger individuals completing their studies. Conversely, 6 graduates, or 23%, were aged 24 to 26 years old, highlighting a smaller but still notable portion of slightly older graduates. Notably, there were no graduates aged 27 to 28 years old in this cohort.

In subsequent years, such as 2012, 2013, and 2014, a consistent pattern is observed with the majority of graduates being 23 years old and below, indicating a consistent trend of younger individuals completing their studies. However, there were variations in the proportions of older graduates across different years. For instance, in 2013, there was a more balanced distribution between graduates aged 23 years old and below, those aged 24 to 26 years old, and those aged 27 to 28 years old. This pattern continued through 2015 to 2019, with the vast majority of graduates falling within the younger age bracket of 23 years old and below. Notably, in 2015, all graduates were within this age range, indicating a particularly youthful cohort.

In the most recent year, 2020, a similar trend persisted, with 19 graduates, or 83%, being 23 years old and below. However, there was a slight increase in the proportion of older graduates, with 3 graduates, or 13%, falling within the age range of 24 to 26 years old, and 1 graduate, or 4%, being between 27 and 28 years old. This detailed a minor deviation from the predominant trend of younger graduates seen in previous years.

Table 2. *The Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age*

Year Graduated		Frequency Count	Percentage
2010	23 and below	5	63
	24 to 26	2	25
	27 to 28	1	12
	Total	8	100
2011	23 and below	20	77
	24 to 26	6	23
	27 to 28	0	0
	Total	26	100
2012	23 and below	17	85
	24 to 26	2	10
	27 to 28	1	5
	Total	20	100
2013	23 and below	7	47
	24 to 26	7	6
	27 to 28	1	6
	Total	15	100
2014	23 and below	8	89
	24 to 26	1	11
	27 to 28	0	0
	Total	9	100
2015	23 and below	12	100
	24 to 26	0	0
	27 to 28	0	0
	Total	12	100
2016	23 and below	11	92
	24 to 26	1	8
	27 to 28	0	0
	Total	12	100
2017	23 and below	20	84
	24 to 26	2	8
	27 to 28	2	8

	Total	24	100
	23 and below	38	97
2018	24 to 26	1	3
	27 to 28	0	0
	Total	39	100
	23 and below	60	94
2019	24 to 26	4	6
	27 to 28	0	0
	Total	64	100
2020	23 and below	19	83
	24 to 26	3	13
	27 to 28	1	4
	Total	23	100
Total		252	

3.3. The Profile of the Respondents in terms of Civil Status

Table 3 presents the profile of the graduates in terms of civil status. Frequency count and percentage were used to treat the gathered data.

The data provided in the table offered a detailed breakdown of the marital status distribution among graduates across several years. In the initial year of 2010, a significant majority of graduates, comprising 7 out of 8 or 88%, were married, indicating a prevailing trend of individuals in committed relationships within that cohort. Conversely, only 1 graduate, or 12%, was separated, with no individuals identified as single, married but not living with a spouse, or single parents.

As the subsequent years unfolded, we observed fluctuations in the distribution of marital status among graduates. For instance, in 2011, the comparable trend continued with a notable proportion, 23 out of 26 graduates or 88%, being married. Conversely, only a minimal percentage, 1 or 3%, represented the single or separated category, showcasing a predominance of individuals in marital unions.

Moving to 2012, the data suggested a continuation of the prevalent trend of marriage among graduates, with 18 out of 20 graduates or 90% identifying as married. In contrast, only 1 graduate, or 5%, reported being single. Notably, none fell into categories such as separated, married but not living with a spouse, or single parent, underscoring a uniformity in marital statuses within this cohort.

The subsequent years demonstrated variations in the distribution of marital statuses. In 2013, all graduates reported being married, suggesting a cohort entirely composed of individuals in committed relationships. Conversely, in 2014, there was a divergence from the predominant trend observed in previous years, with 44% of graduates identifying as single and 56% as married. Notably, none reported being separated, married but not living with a spouse or single parents.

In the following years, the data depicted a mix of marital statuses among graduates, with varying proportions of single, married, and separated individuals. Particularly noteworthy is the significant shift observed in 2017, where a substantial portion, comprising 21 out of 24 graduates or 88%, reported being single. This trend continues in subsequent years, with the majority of graduates identifying as single. However, unlike the complete uniformity observed in 2020, these later cohorts show a slight diversification in marital statuses. While single graduates still constituted the largest group, there were now smaller proportions of married and separated individuals interspersed within the cohorts. This indicates a subtle but noteworthy shift, where the trend of predominantly single graduates persists, yet some variation in marital status begins to reemerge.

Finally, in the most recent year of 2020, all graduates reported being single, signaling a departure from the trends observed in previous years. This marked a significant departure from the trends observed in previous years, where a mix of marital statuses was more common among graduates. This uniformity in the 2020 cohort suggests a notable shift in the composition of marital statuses, potentially reflecting broader societal changes, evolving personal priorities, or specific circumstances unique to that year. This data point stood out as an interesting development, warranting further investigation to understand the underlying factors contributing to this shift.

Table 3. *The Profile of the Respondents in terms of Civil Status*

Year Graduated		Frequency Count	Percentage
2010	Single	0	0
	Married	7	88
	Separated/ Divorce	1	12
	Married but not living with Spouse	0	0
	Single Parent	0	0
	Total	8	100
2011	Single	1	3
	Married	23	88
	Separated/ Divorce	1	3
	Married but not living with Spouse	1	3
	Single Parent	1	3

	Total	26	100
	Single	1	5
	Married	18	90
2012	Separated/ Divorce	0	0
	Married but not living with Spouse	0	0
	Single Parent	1	5
	Total	20	100
	Single	0	0
2013	Married	15	100
	Separated/ Divorce	0	0
	Married but not living with Spouse	0	0
	Single Parent	0	0
	Total	15	100
2014	Single	4	44
	Married	5	56
	Separated/ Divorce	0	0
	Married but not living with Spouse	0	0
	Single Parent	0	0
2015	Total	9	100
	Single	3	25
	Married	6	50
	Separated/ Divorce	1	8
	Married but not living with Spouse	0	0
2016	Single Parent	2	17
	Total	12	100
	Single	5	42
	Married	7	58
	Separated/ Divorce	0	0
2017	Married but not living with Spouse	0	0
	Single Parent	0	0
	Total	12	100
	Single	21	88
	Married	3	12
2018	Separated/ Divorce	0	0
	Married but not living with Spouse	0	0
	Single Parent	0	0
	Total	24	100
	Single	31	79
2019	Married	8	21
	Separated/ Divorce	0	0
	Married but not living with Spouse	0	0
	Single Parent	0	0
	Total	39	100
2020	Single	50	78
	Married	13	20
	Separated/ Divorce	1	2
	Married but not living with Spouse	0	0
	Single Parent	0	0
2020	Total	64	100
	Single	23	100
	Married	0	0
	Separated/ Divorce	0	0
	Married but not living with Spouse	0	0
2020	Single Parent	0	0
	Total	23	100

3.4. Highest Educational Attainment

Table 4 illustrates the highest educational attainment of the respondents, with frequency count and percentage utilized to analyze the gathered data.

In 2010, the majority of respondents, accounting for 6 or 75%, were Criminology graduates, while none possessed MA units. Additionally, 2 respondents, or 25%, held full-fledged MA degrees. Similarly, in 2011, all 26 respondents, representing 100%, were Criminology graduates, with none having MA units or full-fledged MA degrees.

Moving forward to 2012, 19 respondents, or 95%, were Criminology graduates, with one respondent, or 5%, holding a full-fledged

MA degree, and none possessing MA units. The pattern continues in subsequent years, with 100% of respondents being Criminology graduates in 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016, and 2017, and no respondents having MA units or full-fledged MA degrees in these years.

However, in 2018, a slight deviation is observed, with 28 respondents, or 97%, being Criminology graduates, one respondent, or 3%, having MA units, and none holding a full-fledged MA degree. Similarly, in 2019, 63 respondents, or 98%, were Criminology graduates, one respondent, or 2%, possessed MA units, and none had a full-fledged MA degree.

Finally, in 2020, all 23 respondents were Criminology graduates, with none having MA units or holding a full-fledged MA degree. From the results, it was evident that the highest number of graduates pursuing advanced studies was in the year 2010, with 2 individuals holding full-fledged MA degrees.

Table 4. Highest Educational Attainment

Year Graduated		Frequency Count	Percentage
2010	Criminology Graduate	6	75
	With MA units	0	0
	Full-Pledged MA	2	25
	Total	8	100
2011	Criminology Graduate	26	100
	With MA units	0	0
	Full-Pledged MA	0	0
	Total	26	100
2012	Criminology Graduate	19	95
	With MA units	0	0
	Full-Pledged MA	1	5
	Total	20	100
2013	Criminology Graduate	15	100
	With MA units	0	0
	Full-Pledged MA	0	0
	Total	15	100
2014	Criminology Graduate	9	100
	With MA units	0	0
	Full-Pledged MA	0	0
	Total	9	100
2015	Criminology Graduate	12	100
	With MA units	0	0
	Full-Pledged MA	0	0
	Total	12	100
2016	Criminology Graduate	12	100
	With MA units	0	0
	Full-Pledged MA	0	0
	Total	12	100
2017	Criminology Graduate	24	100
	With MA units	0	0
	Full-Pledged MA	0	0
	Total	24	100
2018	Criminology Graduate	38	97
	With MA units	1	3
	Full-Pledged MA	0	0
	Total	39	100
2019	Criminology Graduate	63	98
	With MA units	1	2
	Full-Pledged MA	0	0
	Total	64	100
2020	Criminology Graduate	23	100
	With MA units	0	0
	Full-Pledged MA	0	0
	Total	23	100
Total		252	

3.5. Professional Examination Passed

Table 5 provides an overview of the professional examinations passed by the respondents, with frequency count and percentage utilized for data analysis.

In 2010, all 4 respondents, representing 100%, successfully passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination, while none passed the Civil Service Examination. The trend shifted slightly in 2011, with 6 respondents, or 67%, who passed the Criminologist Licensure

Examination and 3 respondents, or 33%, who passed the Civil Service Examination. Moving to 2012, no respondents passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination, while all 10 respondents, representing 100%, successfully passed the Civil Service Examination. In 2013, 4 respondents, or 57%, passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination, while 3 respondents, or 43%, passed the Civil Service Examination.

Similarly, in 2014, 3 respondents, or 38%, passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination, and 5 respondents, or 62%, who passed the Civil Service Examination. The trend continued in 2015, with 4 respondents, or 67%, passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination, and 2 respondents, or 33%, passing the Civil Service Examination. In 2016, the distribution was evenly split, with 4 respondents, or 50%, passing the Criminologist Licensure Examination, and 4 respondents, or 50%, passing the Civil Service Examination. Subsequently, in 2017, 12 respondents, or 71%, passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination, while 5 respondents, or 29%, passed the Civil Service Examination.

The trend continued in 2018, with 12 respondents, or 86%, passing the Criminology Licensure Examination, and 2 respondents, or 14%, passing the Civil Service Examination. In 2019, 20 respondents, or 57%, passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination, while 15 respondents, or 43%, passed the Civil Service Examination. Finally, in 2020, 10 respondents, or 83%, passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination, and 2 respondents, or 17%, passed the Civil Service Examination.

These results offered insights into the professional achievements of the respondents across different years, highlighting the varying success rates in the Criminologist Licensure Examination and the Civil Service Examination.

Table 5. Professional Examination Passed

Year Graduated		Frequency Count	Percentage
2010	Criminology Examination	4	100
	Civil Service Examination	0	0
	Total	4	100
2011	Criminology Examination	6	67
	Civil Service Examination	3	33
	Total	9	100
2012	Criminology Examination	0	0
	Civil Service Examination	10	100
	Total	10	100
2013	Criminology Examination	4	57
	Civil Service Examination	3	43
	Total	7	100
2014	Criminology Examination	3	38
	Civil Service Examination	5	62
	Total	8	100
2015	Criminology Examination	4	67
	Civil Service Examination	2	33
	Total	6	100
2016	Criminology Examination	4	50
	Civil Service Examination	4	50
	Total	8	100
2017	Criminology Examination	12	71
	Civil Service Examination	5	29
	Total	17	100
2018	Criminology Examination	12	86
	Civil Service Examination	2	14
	Total	14	100
2019	Criminology Examination	20	57
	Civil Service Examination	15	43
	Total	35	100
2020	Criminology Examination	10	83
	Civil Service Examination	2	17
	Total	12	100
Total		252	

3.6. Present Employment Status

Table 6 presents the present employment status of the respondents. Frequency count and percentage were used to treat the gathered data.

Table shows that in 2010, 5 or 63% were regular employees, none was temporary, 2 or 25% were contractual and 1 or 12% was self-employed. In 2011, 8 or 57% were regular, none was temporary, 5 or 36% were contractual, and 1 or 7% was self-employed. In 2012, 12 or 63% were regular employees, none was temporary, 2 or 11% were contractual, and 5 or 26% were self-employed. In 2013, 4 or

27% were regular, none was temporary, 8 or 53% were contractual, and 3 or 20% self-employed. In 2014, 4 or 31% were regular, none was temporary, 6 or 46% were contractual, and 3 or 23% were self-employed. In 2015, 6 or 50% were regular, none was temporary, 3 or 25% were contractual, and 3 or 35% were self-employed. In 2016, 8 or 62% were regular, none was temporary, 2 or 15% were contractual, and 3 or 23% were self-employed. In 2017, 12 or 52% were regular, none was temporary, 7 or 30% were contractual, and 4 or 17% were self-employed. In 2018, 13 or 33% were regular, none was temporary, 26 or 41% were contractual, and 15 or 23% were self-employed. In 2019, 23 or 36% were regular, none was temporary, 26 or 41% were contractual, and 15 or 23% were self-employed. In 2020, 6 or 26% were regular, none was temporary, 9 or 39% were contractual, and 8 or 23% were self-employed.

Table 6. Present Employment Status

<i>Year Graduated</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	
2010	Regular or Permanent	5	63
	Temporary	0	0
	Contractual	2	25
	Self-Employed	1	12
	Total	8	100
2011	Regular or Permanent	8	57
	Temporary	0	0
	Contractual	5	36
	Self-Employed	1	7
	Total	14	100
2012	Regular or Permanent	12	63
	Temporary	0	0
	Contractual	2	11
	Self-Employed	5	26
	Total	19	100
2013	Regular or Permanent	4	27
	Temporary	0	0
	Contractual	8	53
	Self-Employed	3	20
	Total	15	100
2014	Regular or Permanent	4	31
	Temporary	0	0
	Contractual	6	46
	Self-Employed	3	23
	Total	13	100
2015	Regular or Permanent	6	50
	Temporary	0	0
	Contractual	3	25
	Self-Employed	3	25
	Total	12	100
2016	Regular or Permanent	8	62
	Temporary	0	0
	Contractual	2	15
	Self-Employed	3	23
	Total	13	100
2017	Regular or Permanent	12	52
	Temporary	0	0
	Contractual	7	30
	Self-Employed	4	17
	Total	23	100
2018	Regular or Permanent	13	33
	Temporary	0	0
	Contractual	17	44
	Self-Employed	9	23
	Total	39	100
2019	Regular or Permanent	23	36
	Temporary	0	0
	Contractual	26	41

	Self-Employed	15	23
	Total	64	100
	Regular or Permanent	6	26
	Temporary	0	0
2020	Contractual	9	39
	Self-Employed	8	23
	Total	23	100
Total		252	

3.7. Initial Gross Monthly Earning

Table 7 presents the data on the initial monthly earnings of the respondents. Frequency count and percentage were used to treat the gathered data.

Data has shown that in 2010, none had initial gross monthly earnings of 15,000 and below, 1 or 13% had 15,000 to less than 20,000, 2 or 25% had 20,000 to less than 25,000, and 5 or 62% have 25,000 and above monthly earnings. In 2011, none had 15,000 and below monthly earnings, 5 or 36% had 15,000 to less than 20,000, 1 or 7% had 20,000 to less than 25,000, and 8 and 57% had 25,000 and above monthly earnings. In 2012, none had less than 10,000 monthly earnings, 2 or 11% had 10,000 to not less than 15,000, 4 or 21% had 15,000 to not less than 20,000, 1 or 5% had 20,000 to not less than 25,000, and 12 or 63% had 25,000 and above monthly earnings. In 2013, none had 10,000 below and 20,000 to not less than 25,000 monthly earnings, 4 or 27% had 10,000 to not less than 15,000, 7 or 47% have 15,000 to not less than 20,000, and 4 or 27% had 25,000 and above initial gross monthly earnings.

Moreover, in 2014, none had 10,000 below monthly earnings, 3 or 23% have 10,000 to not less than 15,000, 7 or 54% had 15,000 to not less than 20,000, 1 or 8% had 20,000 to 25,000, and 3 or 23% had 25,000 and below monthly earnings. In 2015, none had less than 15,000 monthly earnings, 3 or 25% had 15,000 to not less than 20,000, 3 or 35% had 20,000 to not less than 25,000, and 6 or 50% had 25,000 and above monthly earnings. In 2016, none had below 10,000 monthly earnings, 2 or 15% had 10,000 to not less than 15,000, 1 or 8% had 15,000 to not less than 20,000, 5 or 38% had 20,000 to not less than 25,000, and 5 or 38% had 25,000 and above monthly earnings. In 2017, none had below 15,000 and 20,000 to not less than 25,000 monthly earnings, 11 or 48% had 15,000 to not less than 20,000, and 12 or 52% have 25,000 and above monthly earnings.

Furthermore, in 2018, none had below 10,000 monthly earnings, 9 or 23% had 10,000 to not less than 15,000, 5 or 13% had 15,000 to not less than 20,000, 5 or 13% have 20,000 to not less than 25,000, and 20 or 51% have 25,000 and above monthly earnings. In 2019, none had below 15,000 monthly earnings, 22 or 34% have 15,000 to not less than 20,000, 11 or 17% had 20,000 to not less than 25,000, and 31 or 48% have 25,000 and above monthly earnings. In 2018, none had below 10,000 monthly earnings, 9 or 23% had 10,000 to not less than 15,000, while 5 or 13% had 15,000 to not less than 20,000, 5 or 13% have 20,000 to not less than 25,000, and 20 or 51% had 25,000 and above monthly earnings.

From 2010 to 2019, there was a general trend of increasing initial gross monthly earnings among graduates. In 2010, a majority earned 25,000 and above, and this trend continued strongly throughout the years, with fluctuations in the distribution of earnings across different brackets. Significant shifts occurred over time, such as a broader earnings distribution in 2013 and an increase in lower earnings in 2014. By 2015, the majority of graduates earned 25,000 and above, a trend that persisted into 2018. By 2019, the trend continued with 48% earning 25,000 and above and 34% earning between 15,000 and 20,000, reflecting a sustained preference for higher initial earnings among new graduates.

3.8. Competencies Learned in College which is Useful to their Present Job

Table 8 presents the data on the competencies learned by the respondents in college, which is useful to their present job. Frequency count and percentage were used to treat the data gathered. The data from the table underscores the perceived usefulness of various skills to respondents in different years. In 2010, communication skills were highlighted by 25% of respondents as beneficial to their present jobs, followed by human relation skills at 36%, with other skills trailing behind.

Interestingly, in 2011, no respondents emphasized the importance of communication skills, while human relation skills took precedence at 43%. This trend fluctuated over subsequent years, with varying degrees of emphasis on different skills.

In 2012, while communication skills were only mentioned by 5% of respondents, human relation skills stood out prominently at 53%, indicating their perceived significance. Entrepreneurial skills also garnered attention at 26%. Similarly, in 2013, critical thinking skills emerged as particularly valuable, with 40% of respondents recognizing their importance.

This pattern continued in 2014 and 2015, with critical thinking skills consistently highlighted as beneficial by a significant portion of respondents. The years 2016 to 2020 witnessed fluctuating trends, with different skills receiving varying degrees of emphasis.

For instance, in 2016, communication skills and entrepreneurial skills were noted by 23% of respondents each, while critical thinking skills were not mentioned. However, in 2017, a notable emphasis was placed on human relation and entrepreneurial skills.

Table 8. *Competencies Learned in College which is Useful to their Present Job*

<i>Year Graduated</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	
2010	Below 5, 000	0	0
	5,000 to less than 10, 000	0	0
	10, 000 to less than 15, 000	0	0
	15, 000 to less than 20,000	1	13
	20,000 to less than 25,000	2	25
	25,000 and above	5	62
	TOTAL	8	100
2011	Below 5, 000	0	0
	5,000 to less than 10, 000	0	0
	10, 000 to less than 15, 000	0	0
	15, 000 to less than 20,000	5	36
	20,000 to less than 25,000	1	7
	25,000 and above	8	57
	TOTAL	14	100
2012	Below 5, 000	0	0
	5,000 to less than 10, 000	0	0
	10, 000 to less than 15, 000	2	11
	15, 000 to less than 20,000	4	21
	20,000 to less than 25,000	1	5
	25,000 and above	12	63
	TOTAL	19	100
2013	Below 5, 00	0	0
	5,000 to less than 10, 000	0	0
	10, 000 to less than 15, 000	4	27
	15, 000 to less than 20,000	7	47
	20,000 to less than 25,000	0	0
	25,000 and above	4	27
	TOTAL	15	100
2014	Below 5, 000	0	0
	5,000 to less than 10, 000	0	0
	10, 000 to less than 15, 000	3	23
	15, 000 to less than 20,000	7	54
	20,000 to less than 25,000	1	8
	25,000 and above	3	23
	TOTAL	13	100
2015	Below 5, 000	0	0
	5,000 to less than 10, 000	0	0
	10, 000 to less than 15, 000	0	0
	15, 000 to less than 20,000	3	25
	20,000 to less than 25,000	3	25
	25,000 and above	6	50
	TOTAL	12	100
2016	Below 5, 000	0	0
	5,000 to less than 10, 000	0	0
	10, 000 to less than 15, 000	2	15
	15, 000 to less than 20,000	1	8
	20,000 to less than 25,000	5	38
	25,000 and above	5	38
	TOTAL	13	100
2017	Below 5, 000	0	0
	5,000 to less than 10, 000	0	0
	10, 000 to less than 15, 000	0	0
	15, 000 to less than 20,000	11	48
	20,000 to less than 25,000	0	0
	25,000 and above	12	52
	TOTAL	23	100
2018	Below 5, 000	0	0
	5,000 to less than 10, 000	0	0
	10, 000 to less than 15, 000	9	23
	15, 000 to less than 20,000	5	13
	20,000 to less than 25,000	5	13
	25,000 and above	20	51
	TOTAL	39	100

	Below 5,000	0	0
	5,000 to less than 10,000	0	0
	10,000 to less than 15,000	0	0
2019	15,000 to less than 20,000	22	34
	20,000 to less than 25,000	11	17
	25,000 and above	31	48
	TOTAL	64	100
	Below 5,000	0	0
	5,000 to less than 10,000	0	0
	10,000 to less than 15,000	0	23
2020	15,000 to less than 20,000	11	13
	20,000 to less than 25,000	0	13
	25,000 and above	12	51
	TOTAL	23	100
TOTAL		252	

3.9. The Number of Graduates who Passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination From 2010 to 2020

Table 9 provides insights into the performance of graduates in the Criminologist Licensure Examination from 2010 to 2020, employing frequency count and percentage for data analysis.

Among a total of 252 graduates, 79 successfully passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination. The distribution of passers varied across the years, with notable differences in pass rates. In 2010, 4 graduates, representing 5% of the total, passed the examination. This trend continued with 6 graduates (8%) passing in 2011, while no graduates passed in 2012.

Subsequent years saw fluctuations in pass rates, with 4 graduates (5%) passing in 2013, 3 (4%) in 2014, and 4 (5%) in both 2015 and 2016. However, a significant increase occurred in 2017 and 2018, with 12 graduates (15%) passing each year.

Notably, 2019 recorded the highest number of passers, with 20 graduates (25%) successfully hurdling the examination, represented the peak performance across the analyzed years. In contrast, 2020 saw a slight decline, with 10 graduates (13%) who passed the examination.

These results highlight the variability in pass rates over the years, with 2019 standing out as the year with the highest number of successful examinees. Such insights could inform educational institutions and policymakers in understanding the performance trends.

Table 9. *The Number of Graduates who Passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination From 2010 to 2020.*

<i>Year Graduated</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
2010	4	5
2011	6	8
2012	0	0
2013	4	5
2014	3	4
2015	4	5
2016	4	5
2017	12	15
2018	12	15
2019	20	25
2020	10	13
TOTAL	79	100

3.10. The Present Employment Status of the Criminology Graduates From 2010 to 2020

Table 10 provides an overview of the present employment status of Criminology graduates spanning from 2010 to 2020, employing frequency count and percentage for data analysis.

Among the 252 graduates, a total of 243 were found to be currently employed. The distribution of employed graduates varied across the years, with notable fluctuations in employment rates. In 2010, 8 graduates (3% of the total) were employed, with a gradual increase observed in subsequent years.

Notably, the employment rate peaked in 2019, with 64 graduates (26%) currently employed, representing the highest number of employed Criminology graduates across the analyzed years. This significant surge in employment could indicate favorable job market conditions or enhanced career prospects for graduates during that period.

Conversely, the employment rate dipped slightly in 2020, with 24 graduates (10%) currently employed. While still representing a

substantial portion of the cohort, this decline may warrant further investigation into potential factors influencing employment opportunities during that specific year.

Overall, the data highlights the dynamic nature of employment outcomes for Criminology graduates over the analyzed decade, with 2019 standing out as the year with the highest number of employed individuals. These insights could inform stakeholders in the field of Criminology education and career development, guiding efforts to improve job market readiness and facilitate successful transitions from education to employment.

Table 10. *The Present Employment Status of the Criminology Graduates From 2010 to 2020*

<i>Year Graduated</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
2010	8	3
2011	14	6
2012	19	8
2013	15	6
2014	13	5
2015	12	5
2016	13	5
2017	23	9
2018	38	16
2019	64	26
2020	24	10
TOTAL	243	100

3.11. The Number of Graduates who Proceeded to Advanced Studies

Table 11 offers insights into the number of graduates who pursued advanced studies following their success in the Criminology Licensure Examination from 2010 to 2020, employing frequency count and percentage for data analysis.

Among the 79 graduates who passed the examination during this period, only 5 opted to pursue further education. The distribution of graduates proceeding to advanced studies varied across the years, with notable differences in enrollment rates.

In 2010, 2 graduates (40% of those who passed) chose to pursue advanced studies, indicating a significant proportion of individuals furthering their education immediately after passing the examination. However, in subsequent years, the number of graduates who pursued advanced studies fluctuated.

Notably, there was no individuals who pursued advanced studies in 2011, suggesting a temporary decline in post-licensure education enrollment. The trend continued with minimal enrollments in 2012 and no enrollments from 2013 to 2017, indicating a period of relatively lower interest or opportunity for further education among the cohort.

However, there was a slight increase in enrollments in 2018, with 1 graduate opting for advanced studies. This trend continued with 1 graduate in 2019 and none in 2020, reflecting a gradual resurgence in interest or opportunity for further education among the cohort.

Overall, while only a small percentage of graduates chose to pursue advanced studies following their success in the Criminologist Licensure Examination, the data offered valuable insights into post-licensure education trends within the field. These insights could inform stakeholders in Criminology education and career development, guiding efforts to support and facilitate further education opportunities for graduates.

Table 11. *The Number of Graduates who Proceeded to Advanced Studies*

<i>Year Graduated</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
2010	2	40
2011	0	0
2012	1	20
2013	0	0
2014	0	0
2015	0	0
2016	0	0
2017	0	0
2018	1	20
2019	1	20
2020	0	0
TOTAL	5	100

3.12. The Number of Graduates Employed in Line with their Chosen Profession as Criminology Graduates from 2010 To 2020

Table 12 provides insights into the employment distribution of Criminology graduates across various law enforcement agencies,

including the Philippine National Police (PNP), Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP), Municipal Jail Management and Penology (MJMP), and other related agencies, denoted as ADP officers. Frequency count and percentage were utilized for data analysis.

Among the 243 employed Criminology graduates from 2010 to 2020, only 76 found employment directly aligned with their profession. The distribution of graduates employed in line with their profession varied across the years, with notable differences in employment rates within specific agencies.

In 2010, 3 graduates (4% of the employed cohort) secured positions within their profession, with a gradual increase observed in subsequent years. Notably, the number of graduates employed in line with their profession peaked in 2019, with 17 graduates (23%) securing relevant positions within law enforcement agencies. This surge in employment could indicate favourable job market conditions or enhanced career prospects within the field during that period.

Conversely, 2020 saw a slight decline in the number of graduates employed in line with their profession, with only 4 graduates (5%) securing relevant positions. While still representing a notable portion of the employed cohort, this decline may warrant further investigation into potential factors influencing employment opportunities within specific law enforcement agencies during that year.

Overall, the data highlights the varying employment outcomes for Criminology graduates across different law enforcement agencies over the analysed decade. These insights can inform stakeholders in Criminology education and career development, guiding efforts to support graduates in securing employment aligned with their professional training and aspirations.

Table 12. *The Number of Graduates Employed in Line with their Chosen Profession as Criminology Graduates from 2010 To 2020*

<i>Year Graduated</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
2010	3	4
2011	8	11
2012	10	13
2013	4	5
2014	2	3
2015	4	5
2016	7	9
2017	10	13
2018	7	9
2019	17	23
2020	4	5
TOTAL	76	100

3.13. Reason Causing a Job Mismatch

Table 13 presents the reasons causing a mismatch between graduates' current employment and their chosen profession from 2010 to 2020.

The table presents a summary of various factors impacting a particular situation, breaking them down by their frequency and percentage of total mentions. The factor considered most significant is individual career choices, which was identified 50 times, making up 20% of the responses. This suggests that individual decisions about careers are viewed as the most influential among the listed factors. Following this, technological advancements was also a significant factor, with 45 mentions, representing 18% of the total responses. This indicates that advancements in technology are seen as a major influence as well. Another notable factor is the changing nature of work, which was mentioned 43 times and accounts for 17% of the responses, highlighting its considerable impact.

In terms of moderate significance, both economic fluctuations and misalignment between education and job demands each received 34 and 36 mentions respectively, each representing 14% of the responses. This suggests that these factors were also important but not as dominant as career choices or technological changes. On the other hand, limited networking connections and insufficient career guidance were viewed as less critical, with 31 mentions (12%) and 13 mentions (5%) respectively. This data implies that while networking and career guidance are factors to consider, they are seen as less influential compared to the more prominent issues listed.

Table 13. *Reason Causing a Job Mismatch*

	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Technological Advancements	45	18
Economic Fluctuations	34	14
Changing Nature of Work	43	17
Misalignment between Education and Job Demands	36	14
Individual Career Choices	50	20
Limited Networking Connections	31	12
Insufficient Career Guidance	13	5
TOTAL	252	100

Discussion

This section represents the conclusions and recommendations based on the data gathered.

The Profile of the Respondents in terms of Sex

The presented data delineated the distribution of respondents based on their sex and the respective year of graduation. Notable variations in the male-female ratio were observed across the years. For example, in 2012, the majority of graduates were male (90%), whereas in 2013, the majority were female (87%). Trends emerged, highlighting a consistent increase in the number of female graduates in recent years, exemplified by the years 2018, 2019, and 2020. Conversely, in 2010, 2011, and 2016, there was a more balanced representation of male and female graduates. These findings suggest a dynamic pattern in the gender composition of graduates over time, prompting further exploration into potential factors influencing these variations. The percentage breakdown for each year provided a clear picture of the gender distribution within each graduating class, offering valuable insights for researchers or policymakers interested in understanding and addressing historical gender dynamics within the studied population.

This assumption parallels the study of Dela Cruz (2022) which showed shifts in gender enrollment in various disciplines, with women increasingly entering traditionally male-dominated fields. These shifts may be attributed to changing societal norms, increased opportunities for women, and evolving perceptions of gender roles. Moreover, research on higher education might shed light on factors influencing the gender distribution among graduates. Issues such as access to education, career choices, and societal expectations could play pivotal roles in shaping the observed patterns. Studies may also delve into how institutional policies, support systems, and mentorship programs impact the educational experiences and choices of male and female students. Additionally, the workforce trends and gender representation could provide context for understanding the implications of the observed patterns post-graduation. If more females are entering certain fields of study, it may contribute to addressing gender imbalances in specific professions.

The Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

The presented data delineates the age profile of respondents across different graduating years. Notably, a consistent trend emerged where the majority of graduates fell within the "23 and Below" age category, suggesting a prevailing pattern of relatively young individuals completing their academic programs. The percentages of respondents in the older age groups, specifically "24 to 26" and "27 to 28," exhibited a decreasing trend over the years. This could imply a shift towards a younger graduating population or potentially accelerated academic paths. Years like 2015 and 2016 stood out with a concentration of graduates exclusively in the youngest age bracket, signaling a cohort of individuals completing their education at an earlier age. These findings may prompt further investigation into the factors contributing to these age distribution patterns, such as program durations, entry age norms, or shifts in educational preferences.

This assumption parallels the study of Cuadra et al. (2019) that in many educational systems, students typically enter higher education in their late teens or early twenties, leading to graduation in their early to mid-twenties. The prevalence of this age group suggests that students are following a traditional academic trajectory. Also, academic acceleration, which explores how students can finish their degrees in less time, possibly due to credit transfer policies, intensive course structures, or other program-specific features. Furthermore, the changing demographics and generational shifts in higher education provide insights into why there might be variations in the age distribution of graduates over time. Socioeconomic factors, changing attitudes toward education, and evolving career aspirations could all contribute to the observed patterns.

The Profile of the Respondents in terms of Civil Status

The data on the civil status profile of respondents across various graduating years highlighted interesting patterns and trends in the marital status of individuals at the time of completing their education. Notably, a consistent theme emerged as the majority of respondents were married for almost every graduating year, suggesting a prevalent association between graduation and marriage. However, variations existed, with certain years, such as 2015, 2016, and 2020, showing a substantial proportion of single respondents. This indicated potential shifts in societal norms or demographic patterns that influenced the marital status of graduates during those specific periods. Additionally, there was a noteworthy absence of respondents in categories like "Married but not living with Spouse" or "Separated/Divorced" in some years, prompting further investigation into the factors contributing to these gaps. Understanding the civil status profile of graduates was crucial for gaining insights into the demographic composition of the student population, and future research could have explored the nuanced socio-cultural dynamics that underlay these observed patterns.

This assumption parallels the study of Lynch et al. (2020) which indicates that individuals may delay marriage until after completing their education to focus on career development or personal goals. Also, changing demographic patterns and generational shifts suggests that societal expectations around marriage and education may be in flux. Younger generations may be more inclined to prioritize personal and career development before entering into marriage. Moreover, the influence of educational institutions on students' personal lives could shed light on why graduates tend to be predominantly married. Supportive policies, campus culture, and institutional structures may play a role in shaping the demographic characteristics of the graduating population.

Highest Educational Attainment

The data concerning the highest educational attainment of respondents across various graduating years revealed a consistent trend dominated by individuals who had obtained a degree in Criminology. In nearly every graduating year, the majority of respondents graduated with a Criminology degree, reaching 100% in several instances. Notably, there was a conspicuous absence of respondents indicating educational progression beyond Criminology, with only sporadic instances of individuals having completed Master's level courses or holding a full-fledged Master's degree. This pattern suggested that a substantial portion of the surveyed population did not pursue postgraduate education beyond their initial Criminology qualification. The data could be seen as reflecting specific career trajectories within the field of Criminology or as indicative of the prevailing preferences of graduates in this discipline. The infrequent pursuit of advanced degrees raised questions about the factors that influenced the educational and career choices of individuals in this particular field. Further investigation into the motivations, societal expectations, and industry demands that guided these trends could provide valuable insights into the dynamics of educational and career decision-making within the realm of Criminology.

This assumption parallels the study of Thurgood (2020) which highlight the specificity of educational pathways in certain professions, such as criminal justice or law enforcement. Also, it emphasizes the practical and vocational nature of Criminology degrees, preparing graduates for direct entry into relevant career fields. The prevailing trend of Criminology as the highest educational attainment suggests that many individuals within this discipline may prioritize early entry into the workforce over pursuing advanced degrees. Thus, the sociology of education could offer perspectives on the societal and institutional factors influencing educational choices. Societal expectations, cultural norms, and the perceived importance of advanced degrees in specific fields may shape the observed patterns.

Professional Examination Passed

The data on the professional examinations passed by respondents across different graduating years reveals a diverse landscape of career trajectories within the field of Criminology and civil service. In nearly every year, a substantial number of respondents chose to undertake the Criminology Examination, indicative of their pursuit of careers in criminal justice or related professions. Simultaneously, the Civil Service Examination emerged as a popular choice, reflecting a broader spectrum of career opportunities in government service.

Interestingly, the years 2012 and 2013 stood out, with respondents exclusively focusing on the Civil Service Examination without opting for the Criminology Examination. This pattern suggests a dynamic interplay of individual preferences, career aspirations, and industry demands. The fluctuations in the choice of examinations across the years underscore the evolving nature of professional paths pursued by graduates. The data underscores the importance of examining the diverse choices made by respondents in navigating their professional journeys, shedding light on the multifaceted nature of career opportunities within the realms of Criminology and civil service.

This assumption parallels the study of Aydinan (2019) that in investigating career choices, particularly within the fields of Criminology and civil service, often explore factors such as industry demands, individual aspirations, and the perceived value of specific examinations. Also, it highlights the importance of licensing or certification exams in these fields as indicators of professional competence and eligibility for certain roles within criminal justice systems. Additionally, Career decision-making is often influenced by factors such as economic conditions, societal expectations, and evolving industry demands.

Present Employment Status

The data on the present employment status of respondents across different graduating years revealed a diverse spectrum of career paths and employment models pursued by graduates. In examining the trends, it becomes evident that a significant portion of respondents secured Regular or Permanent employment, indicating a preference for stable and long-term positions within organizations. The prevalence of Contractual employment, while varying across years, suggests a dynamic job market where temporary or project-based roles play a substantial role in certain instances. The consistent representation of Self-Employed individuals underscores the entrepreneurial spirit among graduates, showcasing a subset of the population venturing into independent professional endeavors.

Notably, the absence or minimal presence of temporary employment in many years may reflect a focus on more stable and sustainable career options. Overall, the data illuminates the multifaceted nature of post-graduation employment, reflecting the varied aspirations, industry demands, and entrepreneurial inclinations of the respondents.

This assumption parallels the study of Bates & Hayes (2017) who suggests that individuals, especially recent graduates, prioritize securing long-term positions within organizations as they embark on their professional journeys. Stability in employment is frequently associated with financial security, job satisfaction, and opportunities for career advancement. Additionally, contractual employment patterns could provide insights into the factors influencing the prevalence of short-term roles in certain years, such as industry demands, economic conditions, or project-specific hiring practices.

Initial Gross Monthly Earning

The data on the initial gross monthly earnings of respondents from various graduating years illuminates the financial landscape of recent graduates as they embarked on their professional journeys. Across multiple years, a notable trend emerges, with a substantial percentage of respondents falling within the income range of 15,000 to less than 20,000 and, in several instances, earning 25,000 and above. This pattern suggests a diverse spectrum of income levels among recent graduates, reflecting variations in job markets, industry demands, and individual qualifications.

Notably, a recurring theme is the prevalence of graduates securing relatively higher-paying positions early in their careers, underscoring a positive trend in initial compensation. The data also revealed that the proportion of respondents earning 25,000 and above tended to increase in more recent years, indicating potential shifts in salary expectations or opportunities in the evolving job market. These findings provide valuable insights for policymakers, educators, and researchers seeking to understand the financial starting points of graduates and the factors influencing income disparities across graduating cohorts.

This assumption parallels the study of Asuncion (2019) that on entry-level salaries often underscores the variability in income levels based on factors such as industry, educational qualifications, and regional economic conditions. Graduates from fields with high demand and specialized expertise tend to command more competitive salaries, contributing to the observed patterns. Salary norms and expectations for recent graduates, emphasizing the importance of understanding industry-specific benchmarks when assessing initial earning potentials. Moreover, Changes in industries, advancements in technology, and shifts in labor market demands can impact the availability of high-paying positions, influencing the financial outcomes of recent graduates over time.

Competencies Learned in College Which is Useful to their Present Job

The data examining the competencies learned in college and their perceived utility in respondents' present jobs revealed a nuanced landscape of skills and attributes acquired during academic pursuits. Communication skills consistently emerged as a pivotal competency across all graduating years, underlining the enduring importance of effective communication in the professional realm. Human Relation skills, while varying in emphasis, exhibited a notable presence throughout, suggesting their consistent relevance in the workplace.

Moreover, entrepreneurial skills and critical thinking skills demonstrated fluctuating degrees of recognition, with certain years placing a particular emphasis on these attributes. Interestingly, Problem-solving skills exhibit variability, with some years lacking responses for this competency. The trends indicated an increasing recognition of Critical thinking skills in later graduating years, highlighting the evolving demands of the workforce for adaptable and innovative problem solvers. The data underscores the ongoing significance of soft skills, such as Communication and Human Relation skills, while also signaling a dynamic employment landscape that values entrepreneurial mindset and critical thinking abilities. The absence of responses for Problem-solving skills in certain years prompts further exploration into the factors influencing the perception of this crucial competency.

This assumption parallels the study of Dumlao et al. (2020) which highlight how strong communication skills contribute to career success, team collaboration, and overall organizational effectiveness. Additionally, the skills, encompassing teamwork, interpersonal communication, and conflict resolution, are recognized as crucial for fostering positive work environments and enhancing organizational performance. Entrepreneurial skills, encompassing creativity, adaptability, and innovation, are recognized as essential for navigating dynamic and uncertain business environments. Also, critical thinking is acknowledged as a key competency for navigating complex professional challenges. Furthermore, the perception of problem-solving skills may be influenced by educational approaches, workplace cultures, and individual experiences.

The Number of Graduates who Passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination From 2010 to 2020

The data on the number of graduates who passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination from 2010 to 2020 revealed a fluctuating pattern in the success rates of graduates. In 2010, 4 graduates successfully passed the examination, constituting 5% of the total. The number increased in 2011 with 6 graduates passing, contributing to 8% of the total. Surprisingly, the year 2012 recorded zero graduates passing the examination, reflecting a significant drop. However, in subsequent years, the numbers rebounded, with 4 to 12 graduates passing annually. The highest number of successful candidates occurred in 2019, with 20 graduates passing, constituting 25% of the total. The overall total number of graduates who passed the Criminology Licensure Examination from 2010 to 2020 is 79, with a cumulative percentage of 100%. The fluctuating success rates could be influenced by various factors such as changes in the difficulty level of the examination, variations in the quality of education provided by the institution, and the preparedness of graduates.

This assumption parallels the study of Aydinan (2019) which suggests that the quality of education provided by institutions plays a crucial role in students' preparedness for licensure examinations. Institutions with robust curricula, effective teaching methods, and relevant practical training tend to produce graduates better equipped for licensure examinations. Also, the variations in the difficulty level of licensure examinations can impact pass rates. If the examination undergoes changes in format, content, or difficulty, it can influence the performance of candidates. Some years with lower pass rates may coincide with adjustments to the examination structure. Additionally, adequate resources, faculty guidance, and support services contribute to a positive learning environment and better outcomes in licensure examinations.

The Present Employment Status of the Criminology Graduates From 2010 to 2020

The data on the present employment status of Criminology graduates spanning the years from 2010 to 2020 revealed dynamic patterns in graduates' entry into the workforce. The overall trend indicated a progressive increase in the number of employed graduates, reaching its pinnacle in 2019, with 64 graduates constituting 26% of the total. Variations in employment percentages across different years, such as the lower rates in 2010 (3%) and 2011 (6%) and the higher rates in 2018 (16%) and 2019 (26%), suggest potential fluctuations influenced by external factors. These may include economic conditions, shifts in industry demands, and changes in the nature of

criminology-related professions. The data underscores the importance of monitoring and understanding employment outcomes to enhance career guidance services and align educational programs with the evolving needs of the job market.

This assumption parallels the study of Nayoyos - Refugia et al. (2024) that economic conditions are recognized as influential factors in graduates' employment prospects. During economic downturns, job markets may become more competitive, affecting the ability of graduates to secure employment. Conversely, periods of economic growth may create more opportunities. Additionally, the role of effective career placement services provided by educational institutions in facilitating graduates' entry into the workforce. Institutions that offer robust career counseling, networking opportunities, and internships may contribute to higher employment rates. Moreover, effective career guidance services play a pivotal role in assisting graduates in making informed career choices. Institutions that prioritize career counseling and provide resources for job search strategies contribute to better employment outcomes for graduates.

The Number of Graduates who proceeded to Advanced Studies

The data on the number of Criminology graduates pursuing advanced studies from 2010 to 2020 revealed a notable pattern of limited engagement in postgraduate education within this cohort. Across the specified years, only five graduates, constituting 100% of the total, opted for advanced studies. The data indicated a significant variability in this choice, with 40% of graduates in 2010 pursuing further academic qualifications compared to 0% in subsequent years. This variability suggests that individual preferences, career aspirations, and perceptions of the value of advanced degrees may be influencing graduates' decisions. Factors such as the perceived significance of practical experience in the field, career advancement opportunities, and the specific demands of the job market may play pivotal roles in the decision-making process. Exploring the long-term career trajectories of graduates who pursued advanced studies can provide valuable insights into the impact of postgraduate education on career outcomes within the dynamic field of Criminology.

This assumption parallels the study of Russell-Brown (2021) which suggests that individuals often pursue advanced studies for career advancement and specialization. Advanced degrees can provide a pathway to leadership positions, specialized roles, and enhanced expertise within the criminal justice system. Additionally, the preference for immediate entry into the workforce over pursuing advanced studies may reflect a broader trend seen in various professions where practical experience is deemed valuable. Graduates may perceive that gaining real-world experience holds greater significance than acquiring additional academic qualifications.

The Number of Graduates Employed in Line with their Chosen Profession as Criminology Graduates from 2010 To 2020

The data on the number of Criminology graduates employed in line with their chosen profession from 2010 to 2020 provided insights into the alignment between graduates' education and their subsequent career paths. Across the specified years, a total of 76 graduates, constituting 100% of the total, secured employment directly related to their Criminology education. This suggests a substantial degree of success in matching graduates with professional opportunities within the criminology field. The data indicated some variability in the percentages across years, with notable peaks in 2019 where 23% of graduates entered professions directly aligned with Criminology. Conversely, years like 2014 and 2020 showed lower percentages, indicating a potential fluctuation in the immediate alignment of graduates with their chosen profession during these periods.

The findings align with the study of Thurgood (2020) that underscores the relevance and applicability of Criminology education in preparing graduates for careers within the criminal justice system. Criminology programs are designed to equip students with a range of skills, including investigative techniques, understanding of criminal behavior, and knowledge of legal frameworks, which are highly valuable in professions such as law enforcement, corrections, and security. It also highlights the importance of educational programs aligning with industry needs and ensuring graduates possess the skills and knowledge demanded by the job market. However, it is essential to consider factors such as regional job market dynamics, economic conditions, and changes in law enforcement practices that may influence the immediate employment outcomes of the graduates.

The Reasons Causing a Mismatch between Graduates' Current Employment and their Chosen Profession from 2010 To 2020

The mismatch between graduates' current employment and their chosen profession from 2010 to 2020 was a complex issue influenced by several dynamic factors. Technological advancements played a pivotal role, as rapid changes rendered traditional academic disciplines less directly applicable to evolving job market needs. Economic fluctuations, including recessions and market shifts, led graduates to accept positions outside their desired field to secure employment in a competitive job market. The changing nature of work, exemplified by the rise of the gig economy and remote work, encouraged graduates to explore non-traditional career paths. Furthermore, misalignment between education and job demands, characterized by a lack of practical skills alignment, contributed to graduates facing challenges in meeting industry requirements. Individual career choices, limited networking connections, and insufficient career guidance in educational institutions also contributed to the mismatch. Recognizing these factors was essential for developing targeted strategies to bridge the gap between graduates' skills and the evolving demands of the job market. Initiatives such as curriculum updates, enhanced career guidance services, and efforts to foster networking opportunities played a crucial role in addressing these challenges and better aligning graduates with their chosen professions.

This assumption parallels the study of Guadamor & Eusebio (2017) that technological advancements have been identified as a significant factor contributing to this mismatch. As industries undergo rapid changes and adopt new technologies, traditional academic

disciplines may struggle to keep pace, leading to a gap between the skills acquired during education and those demanded by the evolving job market. Additionally, economic fluctuations, particularly during periods of recession, have been associated with challenges in securing employment in one's chosen profession. Research indicates that economic downturns can result in a reduced number of job opportunities, forcing graduates to accept positions outside their preferred field to gain entry into the workforce.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were formulated:

Majority of the graduates in year 2010, 2012, 2013, 2015, 2017, 2018, 2019, and 2020 were male, and in the year 2011 and 2014 were female, while in year 2016, there were an equal number of graduates in terms of sex. Moreover, in terms of age, majority were 23 and below in the year 2010, 2011, 2012, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, and 2020, while in the year 2013, there was an equal number of graduates with the age of 23 and below and 24 to 26 years old. On the other hand, with regards with the civil status, majority were married for the years 2010, 2011, 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016, while single in the year 2017, 2018, 2019, and 2020. In connection with the highest educational attainment, majority were criminology graduates from year 2010 to 2020.

In line with professional examination passed, majority of the graduates for the years 2010, 2011, 2013, 2015, 2017, 2018, 2019, and 2020 were Criminology Professional Examination passer, and in the year 2012 and 2014 majority Civil Service Examination passers, while there were an equal number of Criminology Professional and Civil Service Examination passers in the year 2016. For the present employment status, majority were regular during the years 2010 to 2017, while majority were contractual in the year 2018 to 2020. In connection with initial monthly income gross, majority earned 25, 000 and above in the year 2010, 2011, 2012, 2015, 2017, 2018, and 2020, majority earned 15, 000 to not less than 20, 000 in the year 2013, 2014, and 2019, while there was an equal number of graduates earned 15, 000 to not less than 20, 000 and 25 000 and above in the year 2016. With regards with competencies, majority had human relation skills in the year 2010, 2011, 2012 and 2016, majority had critical thinking skills in the year 2013, 2014, and 2018, majority in communication skills, human relation skills, and entrepreneurial skills in 2015, and majority in human relation skills and entrepreneurial skills in 2017 and 2020.

Moreover, for the number of graduates who passed the Criminologist Licensure Examination from 2010 to 2020, year 2019 had the greatest number of passers. In the present employment status of the criminology graduates from 2010 to 2020, greatest number of employed criminology graduate was in 2019. There were only 5 graduates who proceeded to advanced studies. The number of graduates who were employed in line with their chosen profession as Criminology graduates from 2010 to 2020, the greatest number of Criminology graduates employed in line with their profession was for year 2019.

The following recommendations were drawn based on the study's conclusion:

A collaborative effort between law enforcement agencies (such as the Philippine National Police, Bureau of Jail Management and Penology, Armed Forces of the Philippines) and educational institutions offering Criminology programs. Leaders in these agencies may engage actively with Criminology program administrators, providing valuable insights into evolving industry requirements to ensure that the curriculum equips graduates with the necessary skills. School administrators may regularly review and update Criminology curricula, with a focus on practical skill development, fostering industry partnerships, and enhancing internship programs to prepare students for a dynamic and diverse career landscape.

Additionally, for current and future Criminology students, active participation in internships, workshops, and continuous professional and career development may be recommended to enhance employability and adaptability. Graduate students may seek interdisciplinary opportunities and engage with industry professionals to stay informed about emerging trends. Lastly, future researchers may contribute by conducting in-depth studies on factors shaping gender dynamics, age distribution, and career choices within the Criminology field. In essence, a collaborative and dynamic approach between academic institutions and law enforcement agencies may be vital for enhancing the preparedness and success of Criminology graduates. This would involve ongoing curriculum refinement, industry engagement, and proactive student involvement in practical experiences and professional development initiatives.

References

- Albina, A. C., & Sumagaysay, L. P. (2020). Employability tracer study of information technology education graduates from Albina, A. C., & Sumagaysay, L. P. (2020a) state university in the Philippines. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 2(1), 100055. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2020.100055>
- Asuncion, R. L. (2019). The status of criminology graduates of Isabela State University in the criminologists licensure examination for the April 2010–October 2014 examinations. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences*, 8(10), 234-253. <https://garph.co.uk/IJARMSS/Oct2019/G-2754.pdf>
- Aydinan, J. J. B. (2019). Employment Array of Bachelor of Science in Criminology Graduates in Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology. *International Journal of English, Literature and Social Sciences (IJELS)* Vol-4, (6). <https://dx.doi.org/10.22161/ijels.46.16> ISSN: 2456-7620

- Bandura, A., & Walters, R. H. (1977). Social learning theory (Vol. 1, pp. 141-154). Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice hall. https://www.asecib.ase.ro/mps/Bandura_SocialLearningTheory.pdf
- Bates, L., & Hayes, H. (2017). Using the Student Lifecycle Approach to Enhance Employability: An Example from Criminology and Criminal Justice. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Cooperative Education*, 18(2), 141-151. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1151139.pdf>
- Becker, G. S. (2009). Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education. University of Chicago press. <http://www.nber.org/books/beck94-1>
- Cooksey, R. W., & Cooksey, R. W. (2020). Measurement issues in quantitative research. *Illustrating Statistical Procedures: Finding Meaning in Quantitative Data*, 23-31. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-15-2537-7_2
- Cooper, M. N., Updegrave, A. H., & Bouffard, J. A. (2019). Predictors of criminal justice undergraduates' intentions to pursue graduate education in criminology or criminal justice. *Journal of Criminal Justice Education*, 30(1), 46-70. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10511253.2018.1448096>
- Cosmiano, H. P. O., Sapuras, K. H. D., Cavite, K. M. P., Calaca, N. I., Cano, J. C., Saguran, J. B., & Ederio, N. T. (2023). Employability of Saint Paul University Surigao Criminology graduates from 2013 To 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8337077106>
- Cuadra, L. J., Aure, M. R. K. L., & Gonzaga, G. L. (2019). The use of tracer study in improving undergraduate programs in the university. *Asia Pacific Higher Education Research Journal (APHERJ)*, 6(1). <https://po.pnuresarchportael.org/ejournal/index.php/apherj/article/view/1315>
- Dela Cruz, J. L. (2022). Tracer study of graduate school graduates of a state higher education institution in the Philippines from 2016 to 2020. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 10(2), 149-154. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1355568.pdf>
- Dumlao, T. R., Lopez, M. H., & Manago, J. G. (2020). Tracing CCI education graduates: How well are we in developing professional teachers. *CC The Journal: A Multidisciplinary Research Review*, 15, 1-8. [https://doi.org/10.59573/emsj.7\(3\).2023.20](https://doi.org/10.59573/emsj.7(3).2023.20)
- Escalona, S. M., & Nabe, N. (2024). Academic performance and licensure outcomes of Bachelor of Science in Criminology Graduates of UM Bansalan College: Inputs for Curriculum Enhancement. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 20(4), 389-401. <https://scimatic.org/storage/journals/11/pdfs/31116.pdf>
- González Guarda, C., & Salazar-Tobar, F. (2023). The current state of criminology in Chile: Between amateurism and professionalisation. *Justice, Power and Resistance*, 6(1), 108-126. http://www.researchgate.net/publication/369739796_The_current_state_of_criminology_in_Chile_between_amateurism_and_professionalisation
- Guadamor, M. L., & Eusebio, J. E. (2017). A tracer study on the BS Criminology graduates in CSU-Piat Campus. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences*, 6(12), 93-101.
- Heang, L. T., Ching, L. C., Mee, L. Y., & Huei, C. T. (2019). University education and employment challenges: An evaluation of fresh accounting graduates in Malaysia. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 9(9), 1061-1076. <http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARBSS/v9-i9/6396>
- Igwenagu, C. (2016). *Fundamentals of research methodology and data collection*. LAP Lambert Academic Publishing. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/303381524>
- Lynch, O., & Windle, J. (Eds.). (2021). *Giving voice to diversity in criminological research: 'Nothing about us without us'*. Policy Press. <https://doi.org/10.56687/9781529215540>
- Maratas, E. N. (2018). Graduate tracer study of BS Criminology of JRMSU Main Campus Dapitan City: Its employability and destination. *International Review Of Humanities And Scientific Research by International Scientific Indexing ISSN (Online)*, 2519-5336. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344160493>
- Marginson, S. (2019). Limitations of human capital theory. *Studies in higher education*, 44(2), 287-301. https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/1571564/1/Marginson_Studies%20in%20HE%20final%2030%20June%202017.pdf
- Millner, A. J., Robinaugh, D. J., & Nock, M. K. (2020). Advancing the understanding of suicide: The need for formal theory and rigorous descriptive research. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 24(9), 704-716. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2020.06.007>
- Mina, J. C., Reyes, E. J. G., & Salas, R. F. (2020). A tracer study of Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT) graduates of Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (NEUST), San Isidro campus. *International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences*, 5(4), 1337-1344. https://ijels.com/upload_document/issue_files/77IJELS-108202054-ATracer.pdf
- Muldong-Portus, L. A. (2018). *Doing social science research: A guidebook*. Philippine Social Science Council. http://books.google.com.ph/books/about/Doing_social_science_research.html?id=WpM9vwEACAAJ&redir_esc=y

Nayoyos-Refugia, J., Dalugdog, W. D., Dausan, A. F., & Villa, E. B. (2024). Unveiling the confidence of criminology practitioners: Delving on research knowledge and attitude. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 5(6), 2209-2222. <http://dx.doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.05.06.23>

Notre Dame of Salaman College (2016). *Notre Dame of Salaman College Revised Handbook*.

Pentang, J. T., Perez, D. R., Cuanan, K. H., Recla, M. B., Dacanay, R. T., Bober, R. M., & Nur-aina, A. (2022). Tracer study of teacher education graduates of Western Philippines University-Puerto Princesa Campus: Basis for curriculum review and revision. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 3(3), 419-432. <http://dx.doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.03.03.12>

Rahman, M. S. (2020). The advantages and disadvantages of using qualitative and quantitative approaches and methods in language “testing and assessment” research: A literature review. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jel.v6n1p102>

Refugia, J. N. (2021). Employment status and the challenges encountered by criminology graduates. *International Journal of Educational Management and Development Studies*, 2(3), 101-120. <http://iiari.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/ijemds.v2.3.178.pdf>

Riva, A. D. (2023). Tracer study on the employment outcomes of bs criminology graduates of earist from 2013-2015. The opinions expressed in the articles are those of the author or authors; they are not necessarily the views of Eulogio—Amangl Rodriguez Institute of Science and Technology, and the Office of the EARIST Research Services., 172. <https://earist.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/EARIST-RESEARCH-JOURNAL-2019-January-June-Final-Revised.pdf#page=178>

Ruiz, D. F. A., Pioquinto, P. V., & Amparado, M. A. P. (2020). Employment status of criminology graduates. <https://osf.io/preprints/osf/r6e9b>

Russell-Brown, K. (2021). Black lives matter in criminology? Let’s prove it. *Race and Justice*, 11(3), 328-337. http://www.researchgate.net/publication/354736679_Critical_Criminology_and_Race_Re-examining_the_Whiteness_of_US_Criminological_Thought

Salmo, J., Pentang, J. T., Perez, D. R., Cuanan, K. H., Recla, M. B., Dacanay, R. T., & Nur-aina, A. (2022). Tracer study of teacher education graduates of Western Philippines University-Puerto Princesa campus: Basis for Curriculum Review and Revision. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 3(3), 1-1. <https://www.ejournals.ph/article.php?id=17079>

Super, D. E. (1973). The career development inventory. *British Journal of Guidance and Counselling*, 1(2), 37-50. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03069887308259350>

Sürücü, L., & Maslacki A. (2020). Validity and reliability in quantitative research. *Business & Management Studies: An International Journal*, 8(3), 2694- 2726. <https://www.bmj.org/index.php/1/article/view/1540>

Swart, L. A., Kramer, S., Ratele, K., & Seedat, M. (2019). Non-experimental research designs: Investigating the spatial distribution and social ecology of male homicide. *Research Methods in the Social Sciences*, 19, 20-35. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/334586066.pdf#page=34>

Thurgood, M. (2020). Transforming pedagogy in criminology. *Scholarship of Teaching and Learning in Criminology*, 17-36. http://www.researchgate.net/publication/339716695_Transforming_Pedagogy_in_Criminology

Tutor, M. V., Orbeta, A. C., Miraflor, J. M. B., & Mathew, B. (2021). The 4th Philippine graduate tracer study: Examining higher education as a pathway to employment, citizenship, and life satisfaction from the learner's perspective. *Philippine Institute for Development Studies*. <https://pidswebs.pids.gov.ph/CDN/PUBLICATIONS/pidsdps1926.pdf>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Cha – Cha A. Guiral

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges – Philippines

Marnie J. Besas

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges – Philippines